

“The sole palladium of the people’s rights”.
Freedom of the pen as a counterpower in Kant and his contemporaries

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Abstract

For Kant's contemporaries, his claim that the “freedom of the pen” is “the only palladium of the people's rights” represented a clear political stance that favoured the thesis of the people's sovereignty and the inalienable individual right to judge the actions of the constituted power. This phrase carried with it the echo of almost a century of political claims and concrete, bloody battles in favour of freedom of expression and the press, from England to the overseas colonies and France.

A constellation of terms such as “bulwark”, “palladium”, “guardian”, “sentinel” or “safeguard” had in fact been used to attribute to the freedom of expression and the press the role of a *sui generis* right, capable of protecting all other rights and, thanks to the collective vigilance that it was able to ensure, of protecting against opposing abuses of power and unjust laws, qualifying itself as a countervailing power with respect to the political powers, closely linked to the right of resistance.

For Kant, too, the question of freedom of thought coincided with the philosophical question of the very nature of human knowledge and, at the same time, with the political claim to a power of the people, permanently opposed to that of the State and able to monitor it, judge it and, ultimately, overturn it.

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1. A right safeguarding the others

In 1709, Matthew Tindal described the freedom of the press - in a formula that would be constantly repeated and interpreted in various ways throughout the century - as the “faithful Guardian” of “all other Libertys, both Civil and Religious”¹:

¹ M. Tindal, *Of the Liberty of the Press; in a letter to a member of Parliament*, in Idem, *Four Discourses*, London, 1709, pp. 293-329: iv.

Secure only the Liberty of the Press and That, in all Probability, will secure all other Liberty. But if That once falls, nothing we hold dear or precious is safe.²

After all, added Tindal, “a Religion that refuses Trial ought to be *suspected*”³.

In 1741, Johann Lorenz Schmidt published a German translation of Tindal’s most famous work, with a 130-page Preface, in which he pointedly reiterated Tindal’s theses on the freedom of the press, including the assertion that the prohibition on making its own judgement on that which pertains to religion and that which pertains to superstition and on communicating one’s judgements to others casts doubt on the revelation and makes it *suspect*⁴.

In the *Critique of pure reason*, Kant used the same argument, as well as the same judicial metaphor⁵, and like Tindal, he also applied it to the civil sphere⁶:

Our age is the genuine age of *criticism*, to which everything must submit. *Religion* through its *holiness* and *legislation* through its *majesty* commonly seek to exempt themselves from it. But in this way they excite a just *suspicion* against themselves, and cannot claim to that unfeigned respect that reason grants only to that which has been able to withstand its free and *public* examination.⁷

To the freedom “consistent with the freedom of everyone else and thereby with the common good”, namely, to the universal principle of the right, according to Kant, “there also belongs the freedom to exhibit the thoughts and doubts which one cannot resolve oneself for *public* judgement without thereupon being decried as a malcontent and a dangerous citizen”⁸. Rational activity is therefore constitutively a public process and the prohibition on criticism therefore coincides with the destruction of reason itself⁹.

In the 18th century, freedom of expression was considered by its defenders to be not merely one right among others, but a right that could protect all other rights.

In 1772, the most famous English polemicist of the period, Junius, made this entreaty to his readers in the *Dedication to the English Nation*, a preface to the edition of his letters:

Let it be impressed upon your minds, let it be instilled into your children, that the liberty of the press is the palladium of all the civil, political, and religious rights of an Englishman.¹⁰

In 1769, Junius had reminded the king, who had unleashed his guards on him, that the crown itself “as it was acquired by one revolution, it may be lost by another”¹¹.

² Ibid, p. 323.

³ Ibid, p. 309 (my Italics).

⁴ (J.L. Schmidt), *Beweis, daß das Christentum so alt als die Welt sey, nebst Herrn Jacob Fosters Widerlegung desselben. Beydes aus dem Englischen übersetzt*, Frankfurt und Leipzig, 1741, p. 16.

⁵ V. ad es. KrV, A 751.

⁶ M. Tindal, *Of the Liberty of the Press*, cit., p. 319.

⁷ KrV, A XI in no. (the last two are my Italics).

⁸ KrV, A 752.15-19 (my Italics).

⁹ KrV, A 738.23-27.

¹⁰ *The Letters of Junius*, ed. by John Wade, London, George Bell and Sons, 1890, vol. 1, p. 88.

¹¹ Ibid., pp. 255-270.

In France, Jean-Paul Marat, who had lived in England from 1765 to 1776, equated, just as Junius had done, the freedom of the press to a “palladium”¹², namely, to an instrument for defence against despotic governments. On 19 January 1790, already facing three arrest warrants for *lèse-nation* because of his inflammatory writings, and in defence of his actions, Marat invoked those same letters by Junius¹³.

Camille Desmoulins also looked to the freedom of the English press: in 1789, he called freedom of the press, together with the declaration of rights, the “palladium” of the republic¹⁴. In 1794, Desmoulins dedicated issue 7 of the “Vieux Cordelier” to the freedom of the press, whose epigraph contained the prophetic motto “Live free or die” and which was published posthumously after he was guillotined. Desmoulins recalled the freedom of the English press and identified the freedom to speak and write as the faculty that, on its own, was capable of bringing about the transition from monarchy to republic.¹⁵ Desmoulins quoted the maxim “d’un écrivain anglais”¹⁶ which is not further specified; in my opinion, he was referring to Junius, who had quoted this maxim at the end of the Preface to the collection of his letters; Junius was in turn quoting “a foreign writer”, “Monsieur De Lolme”, namely, the author from Geneva who had taken refuge in England and whose essay on the English constitution was to have a profound influence on the political discussions that preceded and accompanied the American and French revolutions:

If it were possible for the liberty of the press to exist in a despotic government, and (what is not less difficult) for it to exist without changing the constitution, this liberty of the press would alone form a counterpoise to the power of the prince.¹⁷

The parentheses gave an incidental account of the subversive nature of the power represented by the freedom of the press: in a country ruled by a despotic government, the mere existence of freedom of the press would almost unfailingly provoke a change in the form of government. In the term “counterpoise”, it was therefore the prefix “counter” that indicated the decisive political element.

Freedom of expression and freedom of the press can protect the rights of the people because they are configured, with respect to the powers of the State, as a countervailing power: freedom of the press was in fact explicitly ascribed by De Lolme, together with the right to elect members of parliament, to one of the “pouvoirs que le Peuple exerce lui-même”¹⁸. These are therefore rights

¹² Jean-Paul Marat, *Oeuvres politiques et patriotiques, de Marat l’ami du peuple, député à la Convention nationale, proposées par souscription. Prospectus*, p. 3; in Idem, *Oeuvres politiques, 1789-1793*, ed. by J. de Cock, C. Goetz, Brussels, 1989-1995, vol. 8, pp. 4918-22.

¹³ J.-P. Marat, “L’Ami du peuple, ou le Publiciste parisien: journal politique et impartial”, 102, 19 Janvier 1790, p. 5.

¹⁴ Camille Desmoulins, “Révolutions de France et de Brabant”, 55, 1790, p. 117.

¹⁵ Idem, “Le Vieux Cordelier”, 7, 1794, pp. 123 and ff.

¹⁶ Ibid., 3, 1793, p. 45; Ibid, 7, 1794, p. 153. The same quote in Idem, *Éloge de M. Loustalot, prononcé devant la société des Amis de la Constitution*, in “Révolution de France et de Brabant”, 45, 1790, pp. 253-267: 261.

¹⁷ *The Letters of Junius*, cit., p. 102; in the first edition, in French, from 1771, of the text by Jean-Louis De Lolme, the words “ce qui ne seroit pas moins difficile” were not enclosed in parentheses (*Constitution de l’Angleterre ou État du gouvernement anglais comparé avec la forme républicaine et avec les autres monarchies de l’Europe*, Amsterdam 1771, p. 232 and ff.).

¹⁸ Jean-Louis De Lolme, *Constitution de l’Angleterre*, cit., pp. 220 and ff.

possessed directly by the people *against*, as well as *under*, the powers of the State; this manifests their connection to the right to resistance, as Thomas Erskine remarked on 18 December 1792, during his three-hour and forty-minute speech in defence of Thomas Paine in the trial, *in absentia*, for the publication of the second part of the *Rights of Man*.¹⁹

2. Freedom of thought and principles of government

For Kant, too, the question of freedom of thought coincided with the philosophical question of the very nature of human knowledge and, at the same time, with the political demand for a power of the people, permanently opposed to that of the State and capable of watching over it, judging it and, ultimately, subverting it.

In this sense, the essay of 1784 is exemplary: to the question *What is the Enlightenment?*, Kant replied with an essay in defence of freedom of expression and the press. To the paternalistic and elitist view, which confined freedom of discussion within the narrow sphere of an apolitical communication between scholars²⁰, Kant countered with a conception of the Enlightenment as a process of communication and the view that both with regard to “*matters of religion*” and legislation “there is no danger in allowing [...] subjects to make *public* use of their own reason and to publish to the world their thoughts about a better way of formulating it, even with candid criticism of that already given”²¹.

To deny such a right, or to renounce it, would amount to a violation of the “sacred rights of mankind”²² and would hence constitute for Kant - with a view clearly derived from Rousseau - an act that would be legally “null and void”²³.

Kant also subscribed to the view that freedom of thought is a *sui generis*, eminently political right, capable of protecting and promoting other rights and influencing changes in forms of government:

the inclination and vocation for *free thinking* [...] gradually works back upon the mentality of the people (which thereby gradually becomes capable of *freedom to act*), and eventually even upon the principles of the *government*, which finds it advantageous to itself to treat the human being, who is now *more than a machine*, according to his dignity.²⁴

Kant’s conclusion is analogous to the view held by Jean Louis De Lolme and taken up by Junius, regarding the power of the freedom of the press to effect constitutional change, in despotic

¹⁹ Thomas Erskine, *Speeches when at the Bar on subjects connected with the liberty of the press, and against constructive treasons*, London, Ridgway, 1810, pp. 139 and ff.

²⁰ Eckhart Hellmuth, *Enlightenment and Freedom of the Press: The Debate in the Berlin Mittwochsgesellschaft, 1783–1784*, «History», 83, 271/1998, pp. 420-444.

²¹ WA, AA 08: 41.17-21.

²² WA, AA 08: 39.34-37.

²³ WA, AA 08: 39.01-04.

²⁴ WA, AA 08: 41.32-42.02.

regimes, by virtue of its mere existence (De Lolme's essay on the English constitution was translated into German in 1776²⁵).

The defence of a freedom capable of acting on the "principles of government" exposed Kant to the accusation of undermining the foundations of public safety. In response to King Frederick II, who likened citizens to cogs in the State machine, mere machines themselves²⁶ and presented his "principles" as those capable of "rendre bon & avantageux le gouvernement monarchique"²⁷, Kant countered with the argument that freedom of thought would make citizens more capable of action and lead the government to deem it "advantageous to itself" to respect their dignity (where the transformation of "good & advantageous" into "advantageous to itself" sounded downright threatening).

Kant therefore guarded himself with formal assurances about the inoffensive nature of the freedom of expression²⁸, above all - and paradoxically - in a monarchy in which the sovereign, "himself enlightened, is not afraid of phantoms, but at the same time has a well-disciplined and numerous army ready to guarantee public peace"²⁹.

3. The only palladium of the rights of the people

Freedom of thought was constantly advocated by Kant as a faculty of examination and criticism to be exercised in the two spheres, the religious and the political, in which it was legally restricted. In 1793, he dealt with the first sphere in the essay *Religion within the Limits of Reason Alone* and, in parallel, he devoted the *Corollary* of the second section of his essay *On the Common Saying* to the second sphere, namely, the right to subject the State's activities to public scrutiny. The edicts of religion and censorship were still in force and yet the French Revolution gave the German Jacobins³⁰ – with Kant famously counted among them³¹ – fresh courage. In the writing *On the Common Saying*, Kant described the "freedom of the pen" as "the sole palladium of the people's rights"³².

References to press freedom and English republicanism were widely used in German publications³³: the term "Palladium" had already been used in 1773 by Christoph Martin Wieland

²⁵ J.L. De Lolme, *Die Staatsverfassung von England oder Nachricht von der englischen Regierung, worinn sie mit der republikanischen Form und gelegentlich mit den andern Monarchien in Europa verglichen wird*, Leipzig, Junius, 1776.

²⁶ Frédéric, *Essai sur les formes des gouvernement, et sur les devoirs des Souverains*, 1781, in *Oeuvres posthumes de Frédéric II, Roi de Prusse*, [Basel], 1789, p. 45.

²⁷ Ibid, p. 58.

²⁸ WA, AA 08: 36.35, 41.17-19.

²⁹ WA, AA 08: 41.23-25.

³⁰ The term "Jacobin" at the time was understood in Germany as a synonym for "democrat" and was used as an insulting epithet against anyone who declared themselves in favour of the principles of the French revolution, as Kant did in public and private. See Nicolao Merker, *Alle origini dell'ideologia tedesca*, Bari, Laterza, 1977, pp. 3 and ff.).

³¹ V. Karl Vorländer, *Kants Stellung zur französischen Revolution*, in *Philosophische Abhandlungen*, Hermann Cohen zum 70sten Geburtstag (4 Juli 1912), Berlin, Cassirer, 1912, pp. 247-269.

³² TP, AA 08: 304.15-20.

³³ H.E. Bödeker, "Menschenrechte" im deutschen publizistischen Diskurs vor 1789, in *Grund- und Freiheitsrechte von der ständischen zur späbürgerlichen Gesellschaft*, ed. Günter Birtsch, Göttingen, Vandenhoeck &

– who had presumably taken it from Junius' *Letters*³⁴ - to describe the “freedom to research and say” what one considers “true and right”³⁵.

Kant's assertion that the freedom of the pen is the *only* palladium of the people's rights is only fully comprehensible from the context of the passage, namely, in the context of the treatment of the right to resistance: a positive right to resistance is not conceivable, according to Kant, “for then it would also have to contain a publicly constituted opposing power [Gegenmacht], so that there would have to be a second head of State to protect the people's rights against the first, and then yet a third to decide between the two”³⁶ and so on.

The formulation of the argument on the nature of the freedom of the pen as a palladium, namely as an instrument for the defence of the rights of the people - despite the fact that the latter is not the bearer of any coercive right - is ambiguous and non-linear, as is the entire discussion of the right to resistance. It is therefore up to the reader to reconstruct the overall argument, recovering and connecting the crucial passages that, in the text, are scattered over different paragraphs or kept at a distance by mile-long formulas of devotion to the constituted power and formal assurances of harmlessness (even between “*freedom of the pen*” and “is the sole palladium of the people's rights” there is a long aside, which eloquently begins with “kept within the limits of esteem and love for the constitution within which one lives” and concludes with “so that they do not lose their freedom”).

The argument is based on four premises:

1. the denial of the right to resistance (“the people never has a coercive right against the head of State (insubordination in word or deed)”³⁷);
2. the existence of inalienable human rights, including the right to judge the violation of those rights (“every human being still has his inalienable rights, which he can never give up even if he wanted to and about which he is authorized to judge for himself”³⁸);
3. the sovereignty of the general will (the will of “the supreme commander [...] gives order to the subjects as citizens only by representing the general will of the people”³⁹);
4. the nullity of any law which, although formally enacted, cannot be deliberated by a people upon itself (“*What a people cannot decree for itself, a legislator also cannot decree for a people*”⁴⁰).

Starting with these premises, the argument develops as a dry alternative, of which only one alternative is extensively discussed. That an alternative is at issue is deduced from the first, sibylline statement: “a nonrecalcitrant subject must be able to assume that his ruler does not *want* to do him any wrong”⁴¹: the alternative actually at issue, namely the case in which the non-

Ruprecht, 1987, pp. 392-433.

³⁴ See, in the journal “Der neue Teutsche Merkur”, edited by Wieland, the statement that, “of all the English books I have read, none has ever interested me as much as the letters of Junius” (*London. Prozession in die S. Pauls Kirche. Reynolds Discourses. Junius letters*, in “Der neue Teutsche Merkur”, 1/1798, pp. 86 and ff.

³⁵ C.M. Wieland, *Vorbericht zum Anti-Cato*, “Der Teutsche Merkur”, 3, 1773, pp. 99-126:126; Idem, *An einen Freund, aus Veranlassung der Briefe über die Bibel im Völkerton*, 46, 2/1784, pp. 246-263: 258 and ff..

³⁶ TP, AA 08: 303.10-14.

³⁷ TP, AA 08: 302.25-26.

³⁸ TP, AA 08: 304.04-06.

³⁹ TP, AA 08: 304.22-24.

⁴⁰ TP, AA 08: 304.33-35.

⁴¹ TP, AA 08: 304.03-04.

rebellious subject is forced to assume that the ruler really wants to do him wrong, remains provisionally undefined.

The nonrecalcitrant subject thus assumes, in the event that he considers himself the victim of an injustice, that this injustice is involuntary and that it “occurs only from the supreme power’s error or ignorance of certain consequences of his laws” (to assume that the prince may err or be uninformed is equivalent to the mere assumption that he is human, Kant specifies, preventing the accusation of *lesa maestà*): the subject, therefore, makes “known publicly his opinions about what it is in the ruler’s arrangements that seems to him to be a wrong”, having the faculty to do so, on the basis of the second premise. Such unjust dispositions are, by virtue of the third and fourth premises, legally void acts: it follows that they are “not to be regarded as the real will of the monarch, to whom counterrepresentations can accordingly be made”⁴².

The right that Kant presents as purely negative is none other than the right to declare positive laws null and void (“the universal principle by which a people has to appraise its rights *negatively* - that is, appraise merely what may be regarded as *not ordained* by the supreme legislation, as with its best will”⁴³), which undoubtedly constitutes a countervailing power and - unlike the positive countervailing power that would be represented by the right to resistance - a countervailing power that the law can and must provide for.

Therefore, there is only one countervailing power, a single power that the people possess against the head of a State, for the protection of their inalienable rights, and which constitutes, as such, “the sole palladium of the people’s rights”: the right to judge State provisions and to make their judgement public.

If laws are unjust, they do not apply, according to Kant, even though they have been enacted: if the supreme power refuses to correct them, the subject is forced to assume that injustice is being done to him willingly. His right, however, is only negative: within the legal sphere, he can merely declare injustice, but cannot oppose it using legally coercive means. Considering, however, that unjust laws are not enforceable laws, to demand that they nevertheless bind the subjects is tantamount to doing so by force; it is therefore no longer a question, strictly speaking, of law, but of mere force:

although people have in their heads the idea of rights belonging to them, they would still be unqualified and unworthy to be treated in accord with them because of the hardness of their hearts, so that a supreme power [Gewalt] proceeding merely in accordance with rules of prudence may and must keep them in order.⁴⁴

The formulation of the second alternative appears cautiously distanced from the presentation of the first alternative:

once the issue is not that of right but only of force, the people may [dürfe] also try out its own force and thus make every lawful constitution insecure.⁴⁵

The modal verb [dürfe] amounts to an unequivocal admission of the moral permissibility of resistance to unjust laws.

⁴² TP, AA 08: 305.09-11.

⁴³ TP, AA 08: 304.30-32.

⁴⁴ TP, AA 08: 306.20-24.

⁴⁵ TP, AA 08: 306.25-28.